

Towards More Equitable Parks: A Reproducible Catchment Modelling Approach

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Summary

This paper develops a reproducible method for mapping 15-minute walking catchments to parks across West Yorkshire. By combining greenspace, network, and census data, it identifies who does and does not have accessible greenspace, profiles the communities served by each park, and provides park-level evidence to guide investment, design, and maintenance decisions.

KEYWORDS: Greenspace accessibility, 15-minute cities, OSMnx network analysis, Park equity, Location Quotients

1 Introduction

The health and social benefits of park access and use are well established (Browning et al., 2022; Houlden et al., 2018; Jabbar et al., 2022). The Green Infrastructure Framework’s Neighbourhood Accessible Natural Greenspace Standard aspires for everyone to have “access to and benefit from good quality green and blue spaces within 15 minutes’ walk from home” (Houghton, 2024). Greenspace use varies by age, gender, socio-economic status and ethnicity (Boyd et al., 2018; Richardson & Mitchell, 2010; Roberts et al., 2019; Roe et al., 2016), prompting calls to design parks that better meet the needs of diverse communities. We know that there is heterogeneity in preferred park features across demographic groups and intersectional populations (Barker et al., 2022; Houlden et al., 2024; Sun & Liu, 2026).

The ‘Access to green space in England’ dataset, produced by Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (2024) evaluates neighbourhood-level (Middle layer Super Output Area (MSOA) and Output Area (OA)) access to greenspaces larger than 10 ha within a 15-minute walk, aligning with the Neighbourhood Accessible Natural Greenspace Standard. While valuable for understanding

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neighbourhood access it does not identify *which* specific greenspaces each neighbourhood can reach, limiting its usefulness for park-level interventions. Moreover, the datasets does not asses park quality or the suitability of the park infrastructure for different user groups.

Recent co-production workshops with park managers and policing partners, undertaken as part of the [Safer Parks by Design: Utilising Open Data to Enhance Safety for Women and Girls](#) project highlighted a critical need for park-specific catchment information to support investment decisions, maintenance planning, and safety interventions. This paper presents a reproducible framework for generating 15-minute pedestrian access catchments for publicly accessible parks and greenspaces across West Yorkshire, with plans to scale analysis nationally. This enables us to: 1) understand the communities served by individual parks, 2) identify population groups with limited access, and 3) provide park-level evidence to inform prioritisation of funding and improvements.

2 Methods

2.1 Defining park boundaries and entrances

The Ordnance Survey (OS) greenspace data was used in combination with Open Street Map (OSM) data on greenspaces to define public access greenspaces, including parks across West Yorkshire (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025; Ordnance Survey, 2025). Code is available at <https://safer-parks.github.io/dashboard/>. Greenspaces as defined by OS greenspace and OSM are divided by greenspace type, however the perception of a park typically includes adjoining woodland, recreation grounds, play areas etc. as all elements of a singular park or greenspace. , where greenspaces share a border greater than 10 m they were treated as one continuous greenspace. Only greenspaces/parks greater than 10 ha were included inline with the Green Infrastructure Framework standard (Houghton, 2024).

Calculating contiguous greenspace areas is also beneficial for accurately capturing entrances as often entrances to greenspaces are recorded as the boundary between different greenspace types e.g. woodland onto a playing field and do not capture just the entrances to the greenspace area. Public access greenspace entrances were calculated by combining OS greenspace access points on the park boundaries (within 5m of the boundary) with data on entrances identified from OSM. Further OSM entrances were calculated by identifying where road and walking street networks intersect with the park boundaries, as defined above, allowing the identification ‘official’ and ‘unofficial’ park entrances. This work is currently being validated by audits across parks within the West Yorkshire Combined Authority (WYCA).

2.2 Park catchments

Fifteen-minute walking isochrones were generated from each park entrance using OSMnx and the OpenStreetMap street network (Boeing, 2025). A walking speed of 4 km/h, equating to a 1km walk was used to calculate the 15- minute isochrones also inline with the Green Infrastructure Framework standard (Houghton, 2024). Intersecting output areas from the 2021 census were used to determine population characteristics within park catchments. These include age, economic activity, NS-Sec, self-reported health, religion, household deprivation dimensions and country of birth.

2.3 Location Quotient

Location Quotients (LQ) (Equation 1) were calculated for each park measures for each demographic variable to quantify the distribution of the demographic group compared to the Local Authority in which the park is located. The LQ of output areas not within a park catchment area were also calculated compared to the entirety of WYCA.

- $Park_{dem}$ = Count of demographic group in park catchment area
- $Park_{pop}$ = Total population of catchment area
- $WYCA_{dem}$ = Count of demographic group within WYCA
- $WYCA_{pop}$ = Total population within WYCA

$$LQ = (Park_{dem}/Park_{pop})/(WYCA_{dem}/WYCA_{pop}) \quad (1)$$

3 Results

Within WYCA 519 parks were larger than 10 ha. and therefore included in the park catchment area calculations. For space, we have focused on religion and health demographics within the results section, but full LQ data by park and local authority can be seen in the Appendix.

Census reported Bad or very Bad health was substantively lower in populations who lived within 15-minutes of a park in Calderdale, Kirklees and Leeds (Table 1) where the Location quotient is below 0.8. This trend however is not universal, with parks in all local authorities both serving populations who have substantially higher and lower rates of Bad or Very Bad health than the local authority as a whole (Figure 1). Conversely, the populations with 15-minute access to parks do not report appreciably different levels of ‘Good or Very Good Health’,

Table 1: Census reported Bad or Very Bad Health (2021).

Area	Local Authority Median (IQR) %	Park Catchment Median (IQR) %	Median Park Catchment LQ (IQR)
Bradford	6.84 (4.67 -9.61)	5.59 (4.47-7.28)	0.86 (0.69-1.12)
Calderdale	6.44 (4.07-9.20)	5.87 (4.70-6.84)	0.79 (0.63-0.92)
Kirklees	6.22 (4.20-8.94)	5.49 (4.15-6.97)	0.77 (0.58-0.98)
Leeds	5.53 (3.38-8.53)	5.19 (3.95- 6.68)	0.78 (0.60-1.01)
Wakefield	7.41 (4.67-10.61)	6.92 (5.89-8.44)	0.98 (0.83-1.19)

Figure 1: Swarmplot of ‘Bad or Very Bad Health’ Location Quotient distribution by park, as reported in the 2021 census. An LQ of 1.0 signifies the population of the park catchment has the same level of ‘Bad or Very Bad Health’ as the Local Authority in which the park is located, with an LQ of 0.8 to 1.2 indicating that the park catchment population is broadly similar to that of the local authority. A LQ of <0.8 indicates that the population in the park catchment has a substantively lower level of ‘Bad or Very Bad’ health than the overall population of the local authority. A LQ of >1.2 indicates that the population in the park catchment has a substantively higher level of ‘Bad or Very Bad’ health than the overall population.

Figure 2: Swarmplot of ‘Good or Very Good health’ Location Quotient by park, as reported in the 2021 census. An LQ of 1.0 signifies the population of the park catchment has the same level of ‘Good or Very good’ health as the Local Authority in which the park is located, with an LQ of 0.8 to 1.2 indicating that the park catchment population is broadly similar to that of the local authority.

Most 15-minute park catchments in West Yorkshire had a considerably lower Muslim population than the local authority the park was situated in (Figure 4). The exception can be seen where in some cases the Muslim population is twice to almost five times as concentrated as in the population of local authority. This is in contrast to No-religion and Christian groups where the majority of populations within the park catchment are similar or over represented compared to the population of the local authority.

Figure 3: Swarmplot of Muslim Location Quotient by park, as reported in the 2021 census. An LQ of 1.0 signifies the population of the park catchment has the same number of Muslims as the Local Authority in which the park is located, with an LQ of 0.8 to 1.2 indicating that the park catchment population is broadly similar to that of the local authority. A LQ of <0.8 indicates that the population in the park catchment has substantively fewer Muslims than the overall population of the local authority. A LQ of >1.2 indicates that the population in the park catchment has a substantively more Muslims that the overall population.

4 Discussion

By calculating LQ we effectively control for the underlying demographic population, highlighting where areas those who live within 15-minute walk of a park are markedly different in term of demographics from the local authority as a whole. The detailed insights into the populations who currently do and do not have access to parks, allows Local Authorities to identify suitable locations for new parks and develop plans to ensure current parks are meeting the needs of underserved communities. By providing park level insights into local population the features of parks can also be managed and maintained to best suit the local population. For example, a park with a high proportion of Muslims within a 15- minute walk may best serve the community by providing exercise route for women that allow group exercise in less overlooked areas to support feelings of safety (Barker et al., 2022). Whilst a park that serves an aging population might want to invest in step-free routes and benches to support park use.

5 Conclusion

Whilst these insights are not causal and need further development through a more intersectional approach, By identifying the identify population groups with poor access to greenspace and which parks are serving which communities we can better inform recommendations for park management, maintenance and improvement.

6 Appendix

Figure 4: Bradford LQ by park and census variable. No substantive LQ (0.8-1.2) masked

Figure 5: Calderdale LQ by park and census variable. No substantive LQ (0.8-1.2) masked

Figure 6: Kirklees LQ by park and census variable. No substantive LQ (0.8-1.2) masked

Figure 8: Wakefield LQ by park and census variable. No substantive LQ (0.8-1.2) masked

Biographies

Dr Fran Pontin is a senior research fellow and lecturer at the University of Leeds. Her research applies spatial data science methods to study health determinants and reduce inequalities. Her policy-oriented work leverages diverse data to inform strategies, focusing on food insecurity and public safety.

Dr. Vikki Houlden is an Associate Professor in Urban Data Science at the University of Leeds. She uses quantitative spatiotemporal methods to explore how urban landscapes and greenspaces impact health and well-being. She collaborates with community groups, practitioners, and local government to improve individual experiences of the built environment.

Dr Melissa Barrientos is a research fellow at the University of Leeds. She uses urban morphology, morphometrics, and complexity science to explore urban configuration and city structure and function. Her focus is on spatial analysis as a tool to uncover the influence of built form on urban functioning and how use patterns change and help shape the built realm.

Dr Anna Barker is an Associate Professor in Criminal Justice and Criminology. Her research explores the governance, regulation and policing of urban public spaces, notably public parks, (gendered) perceptions of (in)security and fear of crime and conviviality in public space.

Dr Maeve Murphy Quinlan is a Research Software Engineer. She supports researchers' scientific software development, specialising in developing Open-Source tools to complement geospatial data analysis. She has developed a number of policy-facing dashboards with expertise in ensuring tool accessibility and scalability and championing reproducible methods.

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